

Myofascial Pain Secondary to Duane Syndrome: A Case Study

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ABSTRACT Introduction: Myofascial pain in the trapezius, rhomboids, levator scapulae and sternocleidomastoid is often linked to cervical and thoracic disc degeneration and facet osteoarthritis as well as postural imbalances and muscle deconditioning. **Case Report:** We present the case of a 37-year-old female with Duane Syndrome who presented with chronic neck and mid-back pain. We tried a multimodal approach to myofascial pain management, including physical therapy, nortriptyline 10 mg to address potential central sensitization as well as neuropathic pain, and trigger point injections. Ultimately, the patient underwent ocular surgery, after which her myofascial pain improved. Our other treatment interventions became significantly more effective after the surgery. **Conclusion:** To our knowledge, this is the first case in the literature of extraocular muscle disorders being associated with myofascial pain. It is also the first case of myofascial pain successfully treated by corrective oculoplastic surgery. Extraocular disorders can lead to overuse or repetitive trauma to the trapezius, rhomboids, levator scapulae, sternocleidomastoid and other muscles of the neck and trunk as the patient uses compensatory motions to ease their visual difficulties. This overuse can then lead to myofascial pain and trigger point formation.

KEYWORDS Myofascial pain, Duane Syndrome

Introduction

Myofascial pain in the trapezius, rhomboids, levator scapulae and sternocleidomastoid, is a common cause of neck and truncal pain. It is often linked to cervical and thoracic disc degeneration and facet osteoarthritis as well as postural imbalances and muscle deconditioning. It is not typically associated with extraocular disease[1]. Duane Syndrome is an ocular disorder characterised by a patient's inability to move either one or both eyes outward and inward. Like in other strabismus syndromes, there is a misalignment of the eye. This syndrome affects the 6th cranial nerve,

the abducens nerve, which controls the movement of the lateral rectus muscle. The lateral rectus abducts the eye and controls fixation of outward gaze. In Duane Syndrome, this nerve is either underdeveloped or completely absent[2]. The symptoms of this syndrome include absent to restricted abduction (outward movement of the eyeball) and adduction (inward movement of the eyeball). There is a narrowing of the opening between the upper and lower eyelid during affected eye movement and associated retraction of the eyeball into its socket. The affected eye tends to wander out of alignment with the unaffected eye. This syndrome is congenital and non-progressive[3]. Duane syndrome does not typically affect vision. Therefore, the treatments are aimed at correcting eye movement rather than at correcting vision. Because the syndrome is congenital and does not progress over time, most interventions are aimed at children[2]. Because eye movement is affected, when looking at an object, patients often rotate their heads to focus. Interventions are usually aimed at correcting abnormal head turn. Healthcare providers often employ vision therapy, a type of physical therapy for the eyes and the brain, which is known to be effective for strabismus disorders and difficulties with the convergence of the eyes.

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Prism glasses, another common therapy, use prismatic lenses to realign the affected eye by moving the image closer to the centre of the eye. In this way, prism glasses are useful for correcting the unusual twist to the head and neck as well as the abnormal eye position. Treatment of amblyopia, the wandering eyeball, in childhood can include patching of the stronger eye. By forcing the weaker eye to compensate, the patching strengthens sensory connections between the brain and the eye, improving alignment in the weaker eye[3].

Figure 1: Magnetic Resonance Imaging.

Objective

1. To investigate a potential relationship between adult myofascial pain affecting the neck and torso and congenital disorders such as Duane Syndrome that affect the extraocular muscles.
2. To determine if myofascial pain affecting the trapezius, rhomboids, levator scapulae and sternocleidomastoids, can be treated with oculoplastic surgery to restore satisfactory eye alignment.

Case Study

This is a case of a 37-year-old female with Duane Syndrome that initially presented with chronic neck and mid-back pain. The patient had pain in the distribution of the trapezius as well as pain that radiated over the scalp and into the forehead. There was no precipitating trauma. She experienced occasional numbness and tingling in all four extremities as well as mild weakness in her grasp strength. The pain was not associated with fevers or chills or bowel or bladder changes.

Diagnostically, she had had an MRI of the cervical spine that showed the expected wear and tear changes for her age.

Therapeutically, the patient had experimented with ergonomic changes such as changing her mattress and adjusting her work station. She tried physical interventions such as yoga and massage.

Functionally, the patient worked full-time as a teacher. On physical exam, the patient was normocephalic, anicteric with extraocular movements intact during active testing, and moist mucous membranes. There was a mild loss of cervical lordosis and a mildly exaggerated thoracic kyphosis. Cervical flexion was 60, cervical extension 50, side to side flexion 35 degrees bilaterally and rotation 45 degrees bilaterally. No sensory abnormalities were identified. Motor strength was 5/5 in the elbow flexors (C5), wrist extensors (C6), elbow extensors (C7), finger flexors (C8) and finger abductors (C8). Trigger points were identified in the trapezius, rhomboids, levator scapulae, and sternocleidomastoid muscles.

Methods

The patient was referred to physical therapy for cervical spinal stabilization exercises and a gradual transition to a yoga-based regular exercise program. The patient was prescribed nortriptyline 10 mg at bedtime to address potential central sensitization as well as neuropathic pain. The patient also received trigger point injections in the trapezius, rhomboids, levator scapulae, and sternocleidomastoid muscles.

The patient continued to report severe pain. At her follow-up visit, it became apparent that the patient kept her neck rotated to the left to maintain eye contact with the doctor during the evaluation. When questioned about this, the patient reported a history of Duane Syndrome. She had not mentioned this on her initial visit.

The patient was referred to an oculoplastic surgeon for further evaluation. She was initially resistant to meet with a surgeon given that her vision was normal. Moreover, she had been treated for Duane Syndrome as a child and stated that she had avoided surgery her entire life.

However, after months of persistent pain, the patient consulted with Oculoplastic Surgery and then returned for follow-up. In this patient, the primary extraocular muscle affected was the lateral rectus. While there are several surgical techniques used to correct strabismus caused by Duane Syndrome, in the case of lateral rectus involvement the typical surgical procedure is called a horizontal rectus surgery. Horizontal rectus surgery involves surgically moving the medial rectus insertion approximately 5-6mm away from its original insertion point. This is the most effective way of weakening the medial rectus muscle, which opposes the lateral rectus muscle [4]. Complications can involve facial asymmetry.

Results

The patient presented to us with symptoms consistent with myofascial pain affecting the trapezius, rhomboids, levator scapulae and sternocleidomastoids. The patient did not complain about eye pain and stated that she had no concerns about her visual acuity, so we did not investigate ocular disorders initially.

After further evaluation, it became clear that the patient was in the habit of rotating her head to the left to compensate for the Duane Syndrome affecting her right eye. This motion likely stressed the right sternocleidomastoid and led to muscle imbalances in the other supportive muscles of the neck and torso.

When the patient consulted with an oculoplastic surgeon, she was told that, given her age and advanced condition, non-operative interventions were unlikely to be effective. These included vision therapy, prism glasses, and patching. Surgery to correct the misalignment might be a more effective treatment option.

After the ocular surgery, the patient's myofascial pain in the neck and trunk improved significantly. The trigger points became less sensitive. However, the patient still experienced pain related to her increased use of the opposing and complementary musculature. It took the patient several months to adjust to her new posture and movements.

Our other treatment interventions such as physical therapy, trigger point injections, and nortriptyline, became significantly more effective after the surgery. The patient's pain improved from constant and severe to intermittent and mild. She was able to participate more effectively in a home exercise regimen. Because she could read, write, and type with less neck pain,

she became more productive at work and assumed greater responsibilities. The patient experienced no side effects from her multidisciplinary treatment. She was delighted with the outcome of treatment.

Conclusion

1. To our knowledge, this is the first case in the literature of corrective oculoplastic surgery leading to a >50% improvement in myofascial pain symptoms in the neck and mid-back.
2. Pain physicians treating patients with common myofascial pain syndromes should consider assessing these patients for strabismus and similar disorders of the extraocular muscles. These disorders can lead to compensatory imbalances in the use of the trapezius, rhomboids, levator scapulae, sternocleidomastoid and other muscles of the neck and trunk.

Pain in the muscle and fascia is commonly referred to as myofascial pain. Cervical myofascial pain can follow either overuse or trauma to the affected muscle. The goal of treatment of chronic pain is to reduce pain and improve function. Conventional treatments for myofascial pain can include physical therapy, medications, and trigger point injections[5].

Myofascial pain in the trapezius, rhomboids, levator scapulae and sternocleidomastoid, is a common cause of neck and truncal pain. Common correlations include cervical and thoracic disc degeneration and facet osteoarthritis as well as postural imbalances and muscle deconditioning. Myofascial pain has not previously been associated with extraocular disease[1]. To our knowledge, this is the first case in the literature of extraocular muscle disorders being associated with myofascial pain. It is also the first case of myofascial pain successfully treated by corrective oculoplastic surgery. Extraocular disorders can lead to overuse or repetitive trauma to the trapezius, rhomboids, levator scapulae, sternocleidomastoid and other muscles of the neck and trunk as the patient uses compensatory motions to ease their visual difficulties. This overuse can then lead to myofascial pain and trigger point formation.

Competing Interests

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